

INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8340533>

Annotation: The article reveals the role of information technology in preschool educational institutions. What is the importance of new technologies in the development of children, and what computer games are an effective means for the development of preschool children. An important aspect is the proper use of information technology in a preschool educational organization.

Keywords: Information technologies, technologies in the development of children, an effective means of learning.

INTRODUCTION

Problem statement. The use of information and communication technologies allows to increase the flow of information due to the data available on electronic media and on the network. The problem of developing and implementing information technologies has become urgent technologies in the process of preschool institution management with computer software development, methodological justification and implementation of a quality management system in the educational and educational process.

It turns out that it is not difficult to introduce information technologies to preschool children. As it is now customary to say, "Children of our time are already born with the knowledge of using Information and communication technologies." For most of their adult life, preschoolers are directly connected with the active use of Information and communication technologies: TV, computer, telephone, etc. The variety of information in Internet networks, encourage the child to greater knowledge of the surrounding world. Situational problems in educational software games, develop the logical thinking of the child, it's like "A training life situation, try yourself....", without damage and harm to the condition or psyche of the child, children are not afraid to make a mistake in the game.

Literature analysis. The relevance and problems of using informative and communicative technologies in preschool educational institutions have been considered by many researchers. T.V. Kalinina, relying on the experience of foreign and Soviet researchers, shows in her work how wide the possibilities of preschool children are in mastering new information technologies, and the competent use of computer learning tools immerses the child in a completely new development environment.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Modern pedagogy asserts that the most common and useful direction of the use of information technology in preschool age is its use as a means of teaching in the system of developing kindergarten didactics.

The purpose of the article is to disclose the need to use information technology as a means of developing the environment in kindergarten.

Presentation of the main material.

Currently, it is very difficult to imagine a person's life without information technology, computers, televisions, tablets, etc. The reality of the child is filled with a virtual world, in which there are so many interesting games, cartoons that excite children's imagination and genuine interest. Of course, information technologies are not only entertaining in nature, they are tightly embedded in the educational process for the purpose of learning, cognition, development.

Preschool educational institutions as the first stage of education have also not been left aside, we are talking about the use of information technology (ICT) by preschool teachers to improve the effectiveness of the educational process, for the effective assimilation of knowledge, skills, and skills.

In information technology, there are universal and specialized technologies. Universal technologies are based on the processing and use of information using a computer. These include information technology (IT, from the English information technology, IT) — a wide class of disciplines and fields of activity that are used to create, collect, transmit, store and process information in the subject area based on computer technology.

According to the definition adopted by UNESCO, information technology is a complex of interrelated scientific, technological, engineering disciplines that study methods of effective organization of work of people engaged in processing and storing information, methods of interaction of people with computers and production equipment, their practical applications, as well as social, economic and cultural aspects of this problem.

The creation of an information environment in the preschool primarily depends on the ability, interest and active role of the head in the life of the educational institution.

It is important for the head of the kindergarten to understand that the teaching staff trained in the field of information technology is able to organize in their educational institution such an information environment that will meet all the requirements of educational and methodological content.

For the effective implementation of information technologies in preschool educational organizations, there are the main conditions. The teaching staff who know the technical capabilities of the computer, have the skills to work with it, clearly follow the rules of working with the computer, observe safety and sanitary standards. A typical lesson in a preschool educational organization lasts from 20 to 30 minutes. At the same time, the use of the screen should be no more than 7-10 minutes. After finishing the work, to prevent visual impairment and relieve tension from the eyes, it is necessary to perform eye exercises. Working with innovative technologies makes the teacher's work much easier, so working with them must be controlled by third parties.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The use of ICT allows to increase the flow of information due to the data available on electronic media and on the network. The problem of the development and implementation of information technologies in the management process of a preschool institution with computer software development, methodological justification and implementation of a quality management system in the educational process has become urgent.

Therefore, it is not the poor-quality use of a computer in the work of teachers that carries the problem of different levels of ICT component.

To date, the educator has a fairly extensive choice of ICT in his practice. This is a computer, the use of the Internet, TV, video, DVD, various kinds of multimedia and audiovisual equipment. Educators have become a guide to the world of new technologies for the child.

The use of ICT is one of the priorities of education. The introduction of innovative technologies in pre-school is designed, first of all, to improve the quality of education, increase the motivation of children to acquire new knowledge, and accelerate the process of learning.

One of the innovative areas is computer and multimedia technologies.

The first experience of using innovative technologies in kindergarten revealed that, compared with traditional forms of preschool education, the computer has a number of advantages, such as: 1. genuine interest in the technology itself, 2. imaginative type of information, 3. cognitive activity, 4. individual training, 5. Modeling of life situations, 6. Lack of fear of mistakes made.

The question of the organization of the subject-spatial development environment (PPRS) DOW is currently the most relevant, since an important criterion for evaluating the activities of a preschool organization according to the Federal State Educational Standard is the created subject-spatial environment. PPRS should be variable and rich in content, i.e. equipped with means of education and upbringing - technical, sports, gaming equipment. Therefore, the main task of the DOW is to combine traditional games, toys with bright and visual material and modern technologies in a single developing space. This should be the starting point for working on a whole direction — the creation of an interactive educational environment.

The main forms of ICT use are:

- preparation of group documentation (lists of children, diagnostics of development, planning, monitoring of program implementation, preparation of reports).
- selection of informative and illustrative material for classes, for joint educational activities, design of stands, groups, classrooms.
- creation of presentations in the Microsoft PowerPoint program in various educational fields: "Social and communicative development", "Speech development", "Cognitive development", etc. The presentation helps to combine a huge amount of demonstration material, freeing from a large volume of paper visual aids, tables, reproductions, audio and video equipment.
- using a video camera and programs for editing video files: viewing information material with an overlay is good
the audio they know is nearby, the creation of simple clips, the imposition of voice on video, etc.
- using an interactive whiteboard. The interactive whiteboard allows the child to see himself from the outside, to observe the actions of the partners in the game. Children get used to assessing the situation without completely immersing themselves in the virtual world one-on-one with a computer.
- training programs. Performing tasks, the child learns to plan, to build the logic of the element of specific events, representations, he develops the ability to predict the outcome of actions. He starts thinking before he does. This means the beginning of mastering the basics of theoretical thinking.
- creation of media libraries that are of interest to both teachers and parents.
- creating e-mail, maintaining a DOE website with links to groups.
- the use of the Internet in teaching activities, for the purpose of informational and scientific and methodological support of the educational process.

The wide possibilities of interactive equipment allow you to make classes more interesting, dynamic, ordinary classes turn into an interesting and exciting game or, for example, into an excursion on a given topic. The use of ICT in the educational process helps us to develop various skills in children: attention, memory, fine motor skills that contribute to the development of speech and thinking. With their help, not only the intellectual abilities of the child are developed, but also strong-willed qualities are brought up, such as independence, concentration, concentration, perseverance, which are so necessary for further education and development of the child at school.

New multimedia pasochnitsy in kindergarten allow you to present teaching and developing material as a system of bright reference images filled with exhaustive structured information in algorithmic order. In this case, various channels of perception are involved, which allows you to put information not only in a factual, but also associative form in the memory of children.

The purpose of this presentation of developing and teaching information is the formation of a system of mental images in older preschool children. The use of an interactive sandbox in the classroom allows you to build an educational process based on psychologically correct modes of functioning of attention, memory, mental activity, humanization of the learning content and pedagogical interactions.

The integrated use of information and communication capabilities of the Internet provides great potential opportunities in education. Internet technologies allow:

- automate the learning process;
- qualitatively increase the level of knowledge;
- develop technical skills and abilities necessary for Internet users to communicate and collect information;
- monitor the development and changes of new information technologies;
- learn to synthesize data acquired via the Internet into a single whole.

The computer's ability to reproduce information simultaneously in the form of text, graphics, sound, speech, video, memorize and process data with great speed allows specialists to create new means of activity for children that are fundamentally different from all existing games and toys. All this imposes qualitatively new requirements for preschool education - the first link of continuing education, one of the main tasks of which is to lay the potential for the enriched development of the child's personality. Therefore, it is necessary to introduce information technologies into the system of preschool education and training. Practice shows that at the same time, children's interest in classes increases significantly, the level of cognitive capabilities increases. The use of new unusual methods of explanation and reinforcement, especially in a playful way, increases the involuntary attention of children, helps to develop arbitrary attention. Information technologies provide a personality-oriented approach. Computer capabilities allow you to increase the amount of material offered for review.

All these features indicate the cognitive development of children, the content of communication between them in joint activities. Separately, it is necessary to determine the degree of effectiveness of teaching children using information technology. Foreign researchers distinguish two aspects of learning: reading and writing, mathematics.

According to some studies, a computer learning game promotes children's mastery of reading and writing in kindergarten much earlier than in normal conditions.

CONCLUSION

The use of information technologies in pre-school education makes it possible to increase the efficiency of material assimilation by children, which has a positive effect on their social competence. Also, do not forget that the socialization of a child, which is so necessary for human life, is communication with the outside world, respect for other children and adults, readiness to take care of others and the formation of moral and patriotic behavior and a conscious emotional and value position. Many media loudly repeat about the Internet addiction of the younger generation. The child's consciousness is so immersed in virtuality that it ceases to feel reality, pushing vital self-preservation instincts out of it. The teacher, when familiarizing preschool children with (IT), is obliged to correctly convey exactly the need to use (IT), as described in the article.

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